
THE ROLE OF THE PRIVATE SECTOR IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM

G'aybullayev Sarvar O'ktam o'g'li¹

Xaydarov Bahrom²

Jarasheva Go'zal Bahodir qizi³

Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan

KEYWORDS

Tourism, tourism potential, a state program, tourist diversification

ABSTRACT

This article briefly describes the history and meaning of tourism, the rapid development of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan, foreign experience in the development of tourism, and brief information about the potential of tourism in our country.

2181-2675/© 2022 in XALQARO TADQIQOT LLC.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7451880

This is an open access article under the Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/deed.ru>)

¹ Teacher, Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan, UZB

² Teacher, Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan, UZB

³ Student, Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan, UZB

РОЛЬ ЧАСТНОГО СЕКТОРА В РАЗВИТИИ ТУРИЗМА

KALIT SO'ZLAR:

туризм туристический
потенциал
государственная
программа туристская
диверсификация

ANNOTATSIYA

В данной статье кратко описаны история и значение туризма бурное развитие туризма в Республике Узбекистан зарубежный опыт развития туризма а также краткая информация о потенциале туризма в нашей стране.

Tourism (French: our-sair, travel), tourism-journeying; one of the types of active recreation. Tourism means a place (in a country) where an individual goes for health, educational, professional, practical or other purposes from the place of permanent residence. it is understood that he leaves (travels) for a period of 1 year without engaging in paid activities.

The history of tourism dates back to the beginning of the 19th century. First, organized tourism was organized from England to France (1815). The English priest Thomas Cook, who is considered the founder of tourism, organized the first railway tourism in 1843. After that, he created his own private tourist enterprise, and in 1866, the first tourist groups were sent to the USA. Ibn Buttuta, an Arab traveler in the East, started his journey at the age of 21 and visited almost all the countries of East and North Africa on foot.

Nowadays, tourism has become popular in many countries of the world. Usually, tourism is organized according to tourism routes through tourist organizations. There are many types and forms of tourism (domestic, international, amateur tourism, organized tourism, travel to nearby places, long-distance travel, mountain climbing, sports tourism, etc.).

Today, a number of reforms related to the development of the tourism sector are being carried out in our country. Government decisions, concessions, and the conditions created are an example of this. Complex measures for development as one of the strategic sectors that ensure the improvement of the standard of living and increase the investment attractiveness of our country have been implemented step by step. The Law No. O'RQ-549 was adopted. The law defines the modern programs to be created in the field of tourism, as well as the procedure for their monitoring and development.

In the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkar Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis, "We will continue consistent reforms in the development of tourism in 2021. In particular, special attention will be paid to the development of pilgrimage tourism and domestic tourism. Also, land areas around tourist objects, water and 1 trillion soums will be allocated from the budget for the improvement of road infrastructures" is defined as an important direction. Creating favorable conditions for the development of tourism, primarily in the private sector, increasing the competitiveness and quality of the services

provided, in order to actively and comprehensively promote the national tourism product in the world market, as well as to implement the proposals made in the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 28, 2018, and in 2017-2021 Uzbekistan Five priority areas of development of the republic b Uzbekistan is attracting the attention of the whole world with its many historical and architectural monuments, diverse climate and rapid development. Over the centuries, Uzbekistan has been the Great Silk Road. lining was located on the path of trade, merchants and travelers, geographers and conquerors. At the same time, Uzbekistan is becoming one of the fascinating tourist destinations for those interested in enterprising, culture, history, traditions and exotic countries. Uzbekistan is proud of its architectural monuments that have been preserved from the ancestors to the present day. Historical buildings reflect the past and play a major role in the country's history.

The organizational-economic and organizational-management structures of the tourist services market infrastructure in Uzbekistan are as follows. State management structures at the national level:

☒ State Committee for Tourism Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan: this committee implements the policy in the market of tourist services as a subject of the state;

Ministry of physical education and sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

The Ministry of Justice and the Customs Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan: controls the visa procedure for the entry of foreign tourists;

State educational institutions: education, training, retraining and upgrading of personnel in the field of tourism.

When talking about the development of tourism in our country, we should first of all pay attention to the development of domestic tourism. For example, the number of tourists in the direction of domestic tourism is higher than the number of international tourists in Great Britain, which is among the top ten countries with developed international tourism.

Summing up from the above, it is necessary to consider not only the development of historical and cultural tourism, but also the support of the cultural sector as one of the areas that can provide an opportunity to increase social and economic stability.

References:

1. Uchkun S., Dilshod N. PROCESS OF IDENTIFYING THE SIGNIFICANT ACCOUNTS IN THE REVENUE CYCLE //Journal of marketing, business and management. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 32-36.

2. Dilshod N. XALQARO STANDARTLAR ASOSIDA KORXONALARDA TUSHUMLAR AUDITINI TASHKIL QILISH BOSQICHLARI VA DASTAKLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH //International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2022. – C. 105-110.

3. Najmiddinov D. R., Shodlikov D. E. THE EFFECT OF THE SECRET ECONOMY IN A DAILY LIFE OF THE SOCIETY //Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1A. – C. 56-59.

4. O'G'Li N. D. R., Qizi T. D. Z. **MOLIYA BOZORINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI VA UNGA OID YANGI YONDASHUVLAR** //Journal of marketing, business and management. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 8. – C. 1-4.
5. G'aybullayev Sarvar O. et al. **O 'ZBEKISTONDA ISTE'MOL SAVATCHASI HOZIRGI HOLATINI VA UNI SHAKILLANTIRISH YO 'NALISHLARI** //Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 119-125.
6. G'aybullayev S. **THE PLACE OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY TODAY** //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 11. – C. 116-126.
7. Gaybulayev Sarvar Uktam ugli, Saitov Sirojiddin, & Davlatboyeva Sojida Oybek qizi. (2022). **SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IS A PLACE TO PROVIDE EMPLOYMENT.** Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences, 1(12), 115–119. Retrieved from <http://ijournal.uz/index.php/jartes/article/view/358> DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7429509>
8. Gaybulayev Sarvar Uktam ugli, Saitov Sirojiddin, & Davlatboyeva Sojida Oybek qizi. (2022). **SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IS A PLACE TO PROVIDE EMPLOYMENT.** Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences, 1(12), 115–119. Retrieved from <http://ijournal.uz/index.php/jartes/article/view/358>
9. Gaybullayev Sarvar, Saitov Sirojiddin, & Pulatova Mashhura Xushnadbek qizi. (2022). **FACTORS AFFECTING LABOR RELATIONS AND ITS WAGE.** Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences, 1(12), 125–129. Retrieved from <http://ijournal.uz/index.php/jartes/article/view/360> DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7429572>
10. Yusufjon A. **DEVELOP CREATIVE THINKING IN STUDENTS BASED ON A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH** //CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 03. – C. 5-8.
11. Азимов Ю. **ЎҚУВЧИЛАРДА КРЕАТИВ ФИКРЛАШНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ ВА РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ: АЗИМОВ ЮСУФЖОН, ЎЗМУ Жиззах филиали катта ўқитувчиси** //Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал. – 2022. – №. 7. – С. 302-306.
12. Азимов Ю. **ЎҚУВЧИЛАРДА КРЕАТИВ ФИКРЛАШНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ ВА РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ: АЗИМОВ ЮСУФЖОН, ЎЗМУ Жиззах филиали катта ўқитувчиси** //Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал. – 2022. – №. 7. – С. 302-306.
13. Yusufjon A., Shahzoda U. **DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE THINKING IN STUDENTS IN PHYSICS CLASS** //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 11. – C. 271-275.
14. Tillayev Y., Azimov A., Hafizov A. **Astronomical seeing at Maidanak observatory during the year 2018** //Galaxies. – 2021. – T. 9. – №. 2. – C. 38.

15. Yusufjon A. DEVELOP CREATIVE THINKING IN STUDENTS BASED ON A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH //CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 03. – C. 5-8.
16. Azimov Y. H. et al. Olympism and olympic education at the present stage //Фундаментальные и прикладные исследования в современном мире. – 2016. – №. 13-4. – С. 119-121.
17. Akramovich N. A. THE PRIORITY OF USING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE AGRICULTURAL EDUCATION SYSTEM //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 10. – С. 185-191.
18. Nizametdinov A., Ahmedova H. Elektron ta'lim metodologiyasi rivojlantirishning usullari //Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollari. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – С. 29-31.
19. Nizametdinov, A. A. (2022). OLIY TA'LIM TIZIMIDA AGRAR SOHANING USTUVORLIGI UNDA INNOVATSIYALARNING QULLANISHI. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES, 1(6), 96–98. Retrieved from <https://researchedu.org/index.php/cf/article/view/104>
20. Nizametdinov, A. A. (2022). OLIY TA'LIM TIZIMINING AGRAR SOHASIDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR QO'LLASH USTUVORLIGI. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES, 1(6), 58–60. Retrieved from <https://researchedu.org/index.php/cf/article/view/96>
21. Nizametdinov A. et al. THE IMPORTANCE OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY TODAY //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 11. – С. 251-254.
22. Akramovich N. A. et al. RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNI O'ZBEKISTONDAGI O'RNI //Conferencea. – 2022. – С. 67-69.
23. Nizametdinov Ali Akramovich. (2022). SUN'IY INTELEKTNI KADRLAR SIYOSATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDAGI AHAMIYATI. International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research, 1(2), 251–253. Retrieved from <http://journal.jbnuu.uz/index.php/ijcstr/article/view/171>
24. Bahodirovna D. L., Rakhimovna R. T., Vladimirovna S. L. SPECIAL MEANS OF IMPROVING PHYSICAL PREPAREDNESS FOR SHORT DISTANCE RUNNERS //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 12. – С. 95-99.
25. Nizametdinov A. et al. THE NATURE, CAUSES AND CONSEQUENCES OF THE HIDDEN ECONOMY AND FACTORS AFFECTING IT //Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development. – 2022. – T. 10. – С. 22-39.
26. Nizametdinov A. et al. THE PLACE OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN OUR DAILY LIFE //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 12. – С. 100-124.

27. Akramovich N. A. et al. PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS IN WORKING WITH THE POPULATION IN THE BANKING SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 12. – С. 25-30.
28. Alijon N., Sherzod Y. FACTORS OF INSURANCE ACTIVITY IMPLEMENTATION //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 12. – С. 20-24.
29. Nizametdinov Ali Akramovich. (2022). HISTORY, SUBJECT AND OBJECT OF FORMATION OF "MACROECONOMICS". Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 10(1), 209–210. Retrieved from <https://giirj.com/index.php/giirj/article/view/998>
30. Xolmuradovich X. B., Tuychiyevich X. R. RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT BIZNESNI REJALASHTIRISH //International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2022. – С. 110-113.
31. Rashid X., Mokhichekhra B. The Actions of International Economic Organizations to Solve Global Issues //Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies. – 2022. – Т. 14. – С. 109-118.
32. Khudoyarov R. IMPROVING ECONOMIC GOVERNANCE IN A MARKET ECONOMY //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 10. – №. 2. – С. 610-612.
33. Xudayarov R., Akhror A. BIG DATA TYPES OF EDUCATION SYSTEM AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR USING THEM IN THE FIELD //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 21-24.
34. Nodira T., Rashid X. PROBLEMS OF INNOVATION MANAGEMENT IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 155-164.
35. Xaydarov, B., & Saitov, S. (2022). Raqamli iqtisodiyot tushunchasi va afzalliklari. Zamonaviy Innovatsion Tadqiqotlarning Dolzarb Muammolari Va Rivojlanish Tendensiyalari: Yechimlar Va Istiqbollar, 1(1), 634–635. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/zitdmrt/article/view/5390>
36. Хайдаров, Б. (2021). СОКРАЩЕНИЕ БЕДНОСТИ В РАЗВИТИЕ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИХ РЕФОРМ. Экономика и образование, (4), 288–292. извлечено от <https://cedr.tsue.uz/index.php/journal/article/view/174>
37. Xaydarov, B., & Saitov, S. (2022). Raqamli iqtisodiyot tushunchasi va afzalliklari. Zamonaviy Innovatsion Tadqiqotlarning Dolzarb Muammolari Va Rivojlanish Tendensiyalari: Yechimlar Va Istiqbollar, 1(1), 634–635. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/zitdmrt/article/view/5390>
38. Бахром Хайдаров Холмурадович. (2022). БИЗНЕСНИ РЕЖАЛАШТИРИШ ТАРТИБЛАРИ . PEDAGOGS Jurnalı, 12(2), 139–142. Retrieved from <http://pedagoglar.uz/index.php/ped/article/view/1513>

39. Tuychieva N., Xaydarov B., Rashidova G. MONEY-CREDIT SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 11. – C. 246-250.

40. Nodira T., Xaydarov B., Zafar Q. THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF COMPETITION AND MONOPOLY IN THE ECONOMY //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 11. – C. 241-245.

41. Xaydarov B. IMPACT OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY PROTECTION ON THE DIGITAL ECONOMY //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 11. – C. 163-174.

42. Xolmuradovich X. B., Sherzod ogli A. Z., Rasulbek ogli K. J. BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATINING TURLARI VA SHAKLLARINING AHAMIYATI //MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 18. – C. 140-145.

43. Xolmuradovich X. B. et al. 2022-2026-YILLARDA MO'LJALLANGAN YANGI O'ZBEKISTON TARAQQIYOT STRATEGIYASINING MILLIY IQTISODIYOTNI ISLOH QILISHIDAGI O'RNI //PEDAGOG. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 78-80.

44. Xolmuradovich X. B. et al. " YASHIL IQTISODIYOT" NI MODERNIZATSIYA QILISH VA ISHLAB CHIQRISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING O 'ZARO MUTANOSIBLIGI MASALALARI //PEDAGOG. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 81-85.

45. Бахром Х. Х. БИЗНЕСНИ РЕЖАЛАШТИРИШ ТАРТИБЛАРИ //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 12. – №. 2. – C. 139-142.

46. Xolmuradovich X. B., Tuychiyevich X. R. RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT BIZNESNI REJALASHTIRISH //International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2022. – C. 110-113.

47. Mukhtarov B. A. et al. Manifestation of Corruption in Society //Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities. – 2022. – T. 14. – C. 156-166.